

D6.2 ITAP Progress Report

30.06.2025

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List of abbreviations

BoE	Board of Experts
EC	European Commission
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
HE	Horizon Europe
IRP	Interim Progress Report
ITAP	Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects
M&E	Monitoring and evaluation
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SVS	Strategic Vision Statements
WP	Work Package

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Project Consortium

University Industry Innovation Network BV (UIIN) - Netherlands

TUM International GMBH (TUMInt) - Germany

Momentum Marketing Services Limited (MMS) - Ireland

Instituto Superior Tecnico (IST) - Portugal

Universite De La Reunion (UR) – La Reunion, France

Canarias Universidad Europea De Canarias SL (UEC) – Canary Islands, Spain

Universidade da Madeira (UMa) – Madeira, Portugal

Fachhochschule St. Polten GMBH (STPUAS) - Austria

UC Leuven (UCLL) - Belgium

Magyar Agrar- Es Elettudomanyi Egyetem (MATE) - Hungary

Universitatea Politehnica Timisoara (UPT) - Romania

Vidzemes Augstskola (ViA) - Latvia

In the project, the university partners are represented by or focus the project work on unique departments across their institutions. Specifically:

- UEC: School of Architecture
- UMa: *Higher School of Technology and Management.*
- STPUAS: team of Service Unit Research and Knowledge Transfer
- UCLL: Business Management and Research & Expertise
- MATE: Institute of Agricultural and Food Economics
- ViA: management team and Faculty of Society and Sciences
- IST: Department of Civil Engineering, Architecture & Environment
- UR: ESROI engineering school
- UPT: Digital Transformation Institute - ID/IFR and e-Learning Centre

01

Project overview, aim and approach

An overview of the project's overarching goals, objectives, methodology and consortium.

Project Overview

The **Entrepreneurial & Innovative Universities Accelerator Program** (Accelerate_FutureHEI; thereafter referred as Accelerate Future HEI) project, under the coordination of [University Industry Innovation Network \(UIIN\)](#), launched in January 2023 and is funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe program. Accelerate Future HEI brings together **twelve European partners** from **eleven countries** to develop and implement acceleration services.

Main Aim

Accelerate Future HEI aims to **develop and test acceleration services** to **equip universities with the skills and capacity** to **drive their institutional transformation towards becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative**. To do that Accelerate Future HEI will apply a robust, comprehensive methodology that builds on the status quo and develops a connected vision and set of activities that provide each institution with a tailored institutional transformation action projects (ITAP). Participating in this initiative provides Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) with a unique opportunity to identify key challenges they are facing and dedicate time and resources to develop solutions through a unique ITAP.

The **advantage of participating** is HEIs are not doing this alone but instead receive personalised and peer-to-peer guidance through access to coaches, thematic working group workshops, training workshops and cohort knowledge exchange events. This allows HEIs to take a close internal look at what they want to achieve while receiving external support and guidance to enable them to implement these changes.

Key Objectives

TO IDENTIFY

the **status quo** of the HEI and its ecosystem regarding entrepreneurial and innovative activities.

TO DEVELOP

test and implement acceleration services that help institutions undertake a transformation roadmap and projects

TO BUILD

the capacity of the participating HEIs staff to implement the transformation roadmaps through a **skills development program**.

TO EVALUATE

the strategies from HEIs supervised by an 'Acceleration Board' of **independent experts**.

TO GENERATE

policy feedback to the European Commission as well as provide widespread dissemination of the pilot results to other target groups.

Project Consortium

Accelerate Future HEI brings together **twelve European partners** from **eleven countries** to develop and implement acceleration services.

Led by [University Industry Innovation Network \(UIIN\)](#), this ambitious project brings together twelve European partners from eleven countries to develop and implement acceleration services. The project consortium unites international experts on developing and supporting acceleration services, together with two established HEI consortia, one from the EIT HEI initiative (INCORE) and one from the European University Alliance (E³UDRES²) and EIT HEI Initiative (E.I.N.S). UIIN, together with TUM International and Momentum are referred to as *acceleration partners* to design and deliver the acceleration services and support the HEI *testing partners* as they implement their initiatives.

Our consortium represents institutions across Europe, including the Outermost Regions. The diversity of the partners will enable the development of overarching services that can be applied in different contexts and enable the HEIs to impact their regions.

Project Approach: Methodology

The project's methodology is based on a **gap analysis** which involves a **three-phase approach** to understand the context, strategy, goals and status quo of each HEI testing partner and to provide an evidence-based and solid starting point to identifying areas and opportunities for institutional transformation. The research, development and implementation phases are underpinned and supported by training, evaluation, dissemination and other activities across the project duration.

Current State Analysis

WP2 | M1 – M12

Uncovering the goals for institutional transformation.

Where are HEIs now?

The aim of this phase is to (1) clarify the desired future state and goals for institutional transformation and (2) understand the current state of each HEI testing partner and provide an evidence base for entrepreneurial and innovative activities at the partner universities. Specifically, WP2 involves activities of pre-scanning, asset mapping, focus groups, and surveys.

Developing Roadmaps & ITAPs

WP3 | M6-M18

What needs to change to achieve the goals and how will you do it?

Subsequently this phase builds on the current state data to define and design an implementation plan to achieve the desired future state and institutional transformation goals and objectives, with regards to entrepreneurial and innovative activities including the identification of opportunities and challenges to address in acceleration services and coaching activities. This will be done through the roadmap workshops as well as Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects (ITAPs).

Acceleration services pilot-testing

WP4 | M12 – M48

What will you test and implement?

This phase will support the testing partners in implementing the acceleration services and undertake actions towards institutional change, through a mixture of individual HEI and group-based support. Specifically, HEIs will undergo individual ITAP coaching with experts aligned to their core transformation focus areas, to then work on the implementation of their ITAPs and development of their investment strategy.

Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Program

WP5 | M1 – M48

HEIs will be supported with knowledge exchange and learning opportunities across the full duration of the project. In addition to the personalised coaching sessions, and the feedback, peer-to-peer feedback and mentoring guidance, which will be provided throughout *Phase 1* and *Phase 2*, HEIs will have access to dedicated events and workshops, including thematic Cohort Knowledge Exchange Events and Accelerate Training Workshops.

Acceleration Impact – Monitoring & Evaluation

WP6 | M1 – M48

The progress of the ITAPs will be tracked through a dedicated monitoring and evaluation mechanism to evaluate the impact and policy implications.

Communication and Dissemination

WP7 | M1 – M48

A communication and dissemination plan will be developed to share the transformation stories and the project's key learnings to benefit the project's community.

Management, QA & Policy Feedback

WP1 | M1 – M48

Adequate management and quality assurance processes and tools will be developed to deliver on the project's outcomes and inform policy.

Project Approach: Foundational conceptual model

The methodology within this project is based on a combination of research and practice. One of the key models underpinning the methodology is the **UIIN Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework**[®] - the framework has been developed over 10 years of research and validated in practice to define the key elements of an entrepreneurial and innovative university, and the challenges and success factors associated with HEI transformation to become more entrepreneurial, innovative and engaged.

UIIN Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Framework[®]

Activities

The extent to which HEIs are innovative and entrepreneurial in their activities across education, research, valorisation and governance. This can include facilitating cooperation with surrounding Research & Innovation (R&I) ecosystem actors across all areas of the HEIs, and supporting the transition to knowledge- and digitally-driven HEIs that include research and innovation outputs in teaching.

Mindset

An understanding of the entrepreneurial and innovative mindset across leadership, academics / researchers, professional / administrative staff, and students. This focuses on fostering entrepreneurial and innovative mindsets, not only across entrepreneurial activities but across all activities to develop and nurture a problem-solving approach.

Organisational Support

The organisational mechanisms required for developing both entrepreneurial activities and mindsets within the HEI. These include: strategy and institutional commitment (e.g. HEI research and innovation strategies); support services and activities (e.g. mechanisms to facilitate collaboration and sharing of knowledge, capacity, infrastructure and resources) and incentives and recognition.

External Ecosystem

The external partners and supporting mechanisms in place to ensure impact pathways and the role of the HEI within its regional ecosystem. It defines the degree to which the HEIs facilitate collaboration with surrounding R&I ecosystem actors and engages citizens in solving societal challenges.

Main Deliverables

Below you can see the overview of the project’s deliverables, with the current deliverable highlighted.

Management, QA & Policy Feedback M1 – M48

The plan for how we will ensure we deliver on our outcomes & inform policy

D1.1
DMP M6

D1.2
Initial policy briefing M12

D1.3
Interim policy briefing M30

D1.4
Final policy recommendations report M48

Current State Analysis M1 – M12

Uncovering the goals for institutional transformation. Where are HEIs now?

D2.1
Strategic Vision Statements – M12

D2.2
Synthesis Report – M12

Developing Roadmaps & ITAPs M6-M18

What needs to change to achieve the goals and how will you do it?

D3.1
Roadmap Analysis report - Draft M12

D3.2
Roadmaps Analysis report - Final M18

Acceleration services pilot-testing M12 – M48

What will you test and implement?

D4.1
Summary report - common ITAP issues M12

D4.2
Case study report- ITAPs and results M48

Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Program M1 – M48

The plan for how HEIs gain skills and insights for acceleration & transformation

D5.1
Program overview & delivery plan M12

D5.2
Program delivery progress report & updated plan M30

D5.3
Summary of the learning outcomes M48

Acceleration Impact – Monitoring & Evaluation M1 – M48

We will monitor progress and evaluate impact of ITAPs

D6.1
Monitoring & evaluation plan – M12

D6.2
ITAPs Progress Report – M30

D6.3
Final Impact Report

Communication and Dissemination M1 – M48

We plan to share our key learnings so others can benefit

D7.1
Initial Plan M6

D7.2
Updated plan & first dissemination report M12

D7.3
Interim dissemination report M30

D7.4
Final dissemination report M48

02

M&E implementation and tracking

02 | M&E implementation and tracking

Implementation overview

The M&E methodology, how to use it, and the M&E plan were described extensively in *Deliverable 6.1 Monitoring and Evaluation Plan* submitted in April 2024 (M12). Currently we are in M30 (June 2025) of the project. The testing partners are now familiar with the M&E toolkit (excel file) and have been using it to consolidate and structure the execution of their ITAPs. As of now, with some variation between universities, the testing partners have used the toolkit to set goals and outcomes, define KPIs and targets, and do the first baseline measurements. In regular, roughly 6-month increments, TUM International has conducted Impact Workshops with the testing partners. These allow for guidance, feedback, and best practice sharing amongst testing partners. In the tables below, we have outlined the steps we have taken so far in this process as well as the upcoming steps.

Finalized

Preparation phase: ITAPs were defined by each university within the ITAP workshops. These guide the testing partners regarding the type of actions they have to take.

Phase 1 – Goal and outcome: In the first quarter of 2024, simultaneously to developing the ITAP projects, each university started thinking about their goals and the outcomes of each ITAP and filled this into their own M&E tool.

Phase 2 – KPIs identification and target setting: Based on the agreed upon outcomes, concrete indicators and KPIs were defined and targets were set for each indicator. This process is iterative and adjustments on the KPIs, specifically qualitative KPIs, is occasionally necessary. Additionally, targets have to be reevaluated if they are not reached, or reached too easily.

Second Impact Workshop (September 2024): The second Impact Workshop aimed for each university to present their M&E tool and chosen indicators, opening it up for recommendations and sharing of experiences from peers. TUMint answered any open questions regarding the M&E tool. After this Workshop, the testing partners had to prepare the first Interim Progress Report (IPR) to show their progress in the M&E journey. TUMint provided templates for the IPRs.

Acceleration Board (Board of Experts) Creation: At the end of 2024 TUMint set up an acceleration board with experienced experts that will review the IRPs of the testing partners.

Phase 3 – Data collection process: In the course of 2024 each university began collecting the respective data regarding the defined KPIs. This gave an overview of the status quo of each indicator for Phase 4.

Phase 4 – Measurement of the baseline: Based on the data collected, the indicators should be calculated and evaluated relative to the targets set in Phase 2. This allowed the testing partners to establish the baseline. This phase was completed by the end of 2024 in order to determine how close or far the KPIs are relative to the set goals/targets at the starting point in time (i.e., first evaluation of the KPIs relative to the set target).

Third Impact Workshop (January 2025): The third Impact Workshop aimed to create a platform for the testing partners to share their journey of collecting baseline data and defining target, sharing challenges and solutions with other peers. TUMint guided the group through this process. The universities submitted a second IPR after this Workshop. This report was reviewed by members of the BoE.

02 | M&E implementation and tracking

Ongoing

Phase 5 – Regular monitoring and evaluation: After having collected the baseline data and measured the first status for each of the KPIs relative to the target for each indicator, each testing partner shall start the regular monitoring and evaluation process in 2025. This means defining a time in 2025 where a second batch of data is being collected for each indicator and included in the M&E toolkit (Excel sheet) entering it in the Excel template and observing progress relative to the target. Ideally this is planned and conducted in Q3 or Q4 2025, before the next Impact Workshop. With this step the consolidation phase of the M&E process of each university within this project.

Upcoming

Fourth Impact Workshop (July 2025): The testing partners can share their journey, their challenges and solutions with the group. TUMint will guide this process and answer all M&E tool related questions. The third Interim Report will need to be prepared and will be reviewed by the acceleration board.

Fifth Impact Workshop: In the first half of 2026 the fifth Impact Workshop will be conducted. Again, the aim is to guide the testing partners on their M&E journey and give them the platform to showcase their progress and exchange with peers. The fourth Interim Report needs to be prepared by the testing partners after this workshop.

Sixth Impact Workshop: This final Impact Workshop will be organized at the end of the project timeline end of 2026. Each university will have the opportunity to present their M&E tool and celebrate their ITAP progress. A discussion of next steps at each university to create a long-term and sustainable M&E procedure will be included. The last Interim Report will need to be handed in after the sixth Impact Workshop.

Final Report: Based on all the Interim Reports TUMint in cooperation with all other project partners and the acceleration board will prepare a final report showcasing the process of the universities in becoming more entrepreneurial and implementing their ITAPs.

02 | M&E implementation and tracking

Interim Progress Reports

The M&E process of the testing partners is systematically tracked via Interim Progress Reports (IPRs) that are to be submitted after the 2nd through to the 6th Impact Workshop. The reports are meant to trace the progress in the implementation of the test project(s) described in the ITAPs of each institution. We rely on the M&E methodology to successfully do this.

Each report contains four main sections:

1. Executive summary
2. ITAP project description
3. Progress overview
4. Conclusion & next steps

Section one and two will most likely remain similar, if not the same throughout the iterations, while section three and four will be updated from report to report.

In section three specifically, the steps of the M&E process including the outcome formulation, KPI definition, baseline measurements and target setting, and the reporting are elaborated on. Here we are looking to understand why certain steps were taken, what the process was, how the data collection is being done, what challenges emerge, and how the indicators relate to the set goals.

Review by Board of Experts

While the progress reports give the testing partners the chance to reflect on their process and reevaluate what may need adjusting during the implementation of their test project(s), external feedback is immensely valuable. With the support of the UIIN team, TUMint has selected five experts from industry, university, and public institutions to review the IPRs and share their advice and insights for the implementation of the test project(s) and the successful use of the M&E methodology.

For the second IPRs and for the forthcoming IPRs each BoE member was responsible to read and give feedback on one or two of the reports. If desired, a follow up meeting was organized and facilitated by TUMint between the testing partner and the BoE member, to discuss the feedback. In the upcoming Impact Workshop this process will be reflected on and adjusted based on the feedback shared by the testing partners.

Prof. Dr. Enno Masurel

Dr. Natascha Eckert

Richard Tuffs

Daniela Marzavan

Dr. Adrian Solomon

03

Summary of IPRs

03 | Summary of IPRs

ITAP project description

All partner institutions have developed ITAPs that are tailored to their unique missions, institutional capacities, and regional contexts. While the scope and focus of each project differ, they are united by a shared commitment to fostering innovation, entrepreneurship, and institutional transformation in higher education. The development process was often iterative, with many universities revising their initial plans to better align strategic ambitions with practical feasibility. This involved extensive internal consultation, input from external mentors, and adjustments based on stakeholder feedback. As a result, each ITAP reflects both a clear institutional vision and a flexible approach to change.

Below is a brief overview of each:

IST – Instituto Superior Técnico (Portugal) IST's ITAP supports the university's ambition to become a globally oriented, innovation-driven institution by strengthening internal collaboration and external engagement. It targets improved coordination among departments and aims to create a new environment where innovation and entrepreneurship are embedded in education, research, and professional development.

MATE – Hungarian University of Agricultural and Life Sciences (Hungary) MATE's ITAP aims to guide the university's transformation into a more entrepreneurial and innovative institution in response to technological and societal challenges. It introduces a methodology for institutional change, focused on aligning educational goals with practical outcomes, strategic planning, and measurable progress.

STPUAS – St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (Austria) STPUAS's ITAP seeks to enhance the university's societal contribution by improving knowledge transfer, building new internal structures, and strengthening collaboration between research, teaching, and innovation. It promotes a more inclusive and solution-oriented institutional culture through better support systems and recognition for entrepreneurial activity.

UCLL – UC Leuven-Limburg (Belgium) UCLL's two ITAPs pursue institutional transformation by combining research and service delivery with skills development for students and staff. One focuses on working with regional partners to create societal and sustainable impact, while the other supports internal initiatives that build entrepreneurial capacity and foster innovation.

UEC – Universidad Europea de Canarias (Spain) UEC's ITAP aims to integrate innovation and entrepreneurship into its academic model by strengthening partnerships and connecting students with professional environments. It supports practical, interdisciplinary learning experiences and promotes a culture of collaboration, creativity, and international engagement.

UMa – Universidade da Madeira (Portugal) UMa's ITAP focuses on digital innovation and sustainable practices to enhance education and professional integration. The university aims to expand global networks, promote environmentally responsible solutions, and prepare students for evolving job markets through curricular change and strategic partnerships.

UR – Université de La Réunion (France) UR's ITAP aims to position the university as a regional leader through mindset development and capacity building, as well as strengthening collaboration with industry partners. It emphasizes creating an innovation hub in collaboration with local actors by providing services, equipment and expertise, and developing real innovation and entrepreneurial skills among students.

ViA – Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences (Latvia) ViA's ITAP is designed to increase the university's role in the regional innovation ecosystem by promoting entrepreneurship and leadership among students, staff, and faculty. The project seeks to improve business-relevant skills, support collaboration with local enterprises, and build institutional capacity for innovation.

03 | Summary of IPRs

ITAP project description cont.

UPT – Universitatea Politehnica Timișoara (Romania) UPT’s ITAP focuses on digital transformation across teaching, research, and community engagement, with an emphasis on education reform and institutional modernization. The project includes the development of new programs, partnerships, and digital tools to support innovation and sustainability.

Progress overview

Following the submission of the first interim progress reports (IPRs) in October 2024, which focused primarily on planning activities and early-stage design, the second round of reports in May 2025 reveals a clear transition toward implementation and refinement. In the initial phase, institutions concentrated on establishing governance structures, defining their ITAP goals, and drafting outcome and indicator frameworks. By the second reporting period, however, tangible progress had been made: activities were being piloted, data collection processes had begun, and institutions were actively adapting their plans based on early feedback and institutional learning. This section focuses primarily on findings from the second interim reports, which offer the most comprehensive and up-to-date insight into ITAP implementation across the consortium.

Across all partners, implementation has generally followed five key steps: outcome formulation, KPI definition, baseline measurement and target setting, and early reporting and evaluation. This section provides a summary of consortium-wide progress in each area, followed by a breakdown of challenges as described in both interim reporting rounds. While each institution’s path reflects its specific context and priorities, common patterns have emerged—highlighting both shared milestones and differences in pace, approach, and institutional readiness for transformation.

Step 1: Outcome Formulation

Summary

All nine institutions successfully completed the formulation of their ITAP outcomes. This step involved defining what institutional transformation would look like in each context and ensuring that the outcomes aligned with internal strategic goals, mission statements, and regional priorities. Many universities described this step as a collaborative process, involving staff workshops, cross-departmental meetings, and input from both academic and administrative leadership. The outcomes commonly reflected ambitions to strengthen entrepreneurship, innovation, collaboration, and capacity building.

Challenges described in IPR 1

Some institutions found it challenging to align the diverse expectations and perspectives of internal stakeholders during the outcome formulation phase. The process often required multiple revisions to ensure outcomes were both aspirational and realistic, while also specific enough to guide implementation. For universities with broad or strategically complex goals, articulating clear, actionable outcomes proved especially difficult.

Challenges described in IPR 2

Some partners noted that outcome formulation required multiple revisions to ensure coherence and measurability. For institutions with broader or more abstract goals, translating ambition into specific outcomes posed a challenge, particularly where cross-unit alignment was limited or where terminology needed to be clarified.

03 | Summary of IPRs

Progress overview cont.

Step 2: KPI Definition

Summary

Most institutions had defined a set of KPIs by the second reporting period. These indicators were intended to track both activities (e.g. number of participants, workshops, collaborations) and broader institutional shifts (e.g. mindset change, cross-sector engagement). In many cases, the KPIs were shaped with the help of external mentoring or adapted from existing institutional performance tools.

Challenges described in IPR 1 and IPR 2

Defining meaningful and measurable KPIs was a key challenge across several institutions. Difficulties included translating qualitative goals, such as cultural change or mindset shifts, into quantifiable indicators, and identifying metrics that reflected both institutional ambition and practical feasibility. A lack of robust internal monitoring systems and unclear data responsibilities further complicated this step. In some cases, the institutional culture had limited experience with formal evaluation, which slowed progress in selecting appropriate indicators.

Step 3 & 4: Baseline Measurement and Target Setting

Summary

Progress on baseline measurement and target setting varied widely across the consortium. A few universities had already gathered baseline data and established quantitative targets for key indicators. Others were in earlier stages, either planning data collection activities or piloting internal tools such as surveys or audit frameworks. In many cases, targets were set with reference to strategic planning timelines (e.g. 2030), and some institutions had begun the process of formal validation with senior leadership.

Challenges described in IPR 1

Challenges in this phase centered around data availability and clarity. Institutions struggled to locate reliable baseline data, especially where indicators were new or not tracked systematically. Fragmented data ownership, limited historical tracking, and non-aligned survey cycles made it difficult to establish consistent baselines. In some cases, institutions had to consider their starting point as "zero" for strategic goals, making target setting more speculative or dependent on future developments.

Challenges described in IPR 2

Institutions that lacked prior M&E systems or centralized data infrastructure found it difficult to identify reliable baselines. There were also concerns about data ownership, especially when indicators depended on information held by other departments or external partners. Setting realistic targets was further complicated by uncertainty about institutional capacity or future resource allocation.

03 | Summary of IPRs

Progress overview cont.

Step 5: Reporting of Results and Evaluation of Progress

Summary

Only a few institutions had fully entered the phase of structured reporting and evaluation by the time of the second interim report. Where it had begun, evaluation focused on early outputs such as participation numbers, event delivery, and internal awareness. In most cases, institutions used informal review processes—working groups, reflective meetings, or stakeholder feedback, to assess their initial progress and make adjustments.

Challenges described in IRP 2

A common theme was that institutions needed more time and experience with their indicators before producing meaningful evaluation results. Without complete baselines or validated KPIs, many preferred to wait before drawing conclusions about impact. Nonetheless, the emphasis on iterative learning was evident across the consortium.

Conclusions & next steps

Across the consortium, institutions have moved from planning and design into the early phases of implementation, with ITAPs becoming more visibly embedded in their strategic and operational activities. Most universities report increased institutional engagement, clearer ownership of transformation goals, and early signs of cultural or procedural change. While the pace and scale of implementation vary, all partners demonstrate commitment to the long-term vision of becoming more entrepreneurial, innovative, and externally engaged.

Looking ahead, partners plan to consolidate their progress by finalizing baseline data collection, refining indicators, and integrating ITAP actions into broader institutional structures. Many universities also intend to scale successful pilot initiatives, expand stakeholder involvement, and improve internal systems for monitoring and evaluation. The upcoming phase will emphasize sustainability, capacity-building, and using evidence-based insights to guide strategic decision-making and further embed transformation within the institution.

04 | Annex

See Interim Progress Reports (one and two) of all nine testing partners and Board of Experts feedback.

Link to reports and feedback: <https://tum.workplace.datto.com/filelink/60764-a649bbd-b9d5301032-2>

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